

DEVELOPMENT OF A NANOCOMPOSITE TO REDUCE HYDROCARBON ABSORPTION

J. Powell, A. Lechevretel and J. Wiggers
Pera Innovation Limited, Nottingham Road, Melton Mowbray
Leicestershire LE13 0PB, UK
jonathan.powell@pera.com , anne.lechevretel@pera.com

SUMMARY

The value of incorporating nanoclay particles into polymer matrices and their influence on mechanical and absorption properties of the nanocomposite has been investigated. Techniques to assess absorption of hydrocarbons have been developed and results indicate that nanoclay particles may limit the up-take of hydrocarbons in polyolefin materials.

Keywords: nanoclays, impact strength, absorption, diffusion, exfoliation

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that polyethylene and polypropylene are capable of absorbing hydrocarbons, and this limits their use in many commercially significant areas. This paper seeks routes to lower that absorption of hydrocarbons by informed materials design. At the same time the paper defines routes to measure material absorption, and its more fundamental property, the diffusion rate for hydrocarbons through materials.

Nanoclays blended with polymeric materials to form nanofilled polymer composites have generated much interest in the last decade. They confer significantly enhanced performance to the base polymer even at small loading of the nanoclay by capitalizing on their nanometre-size and high surface area per unit mass [1]. The objective of this project is to develop an exfoliated nanocomposite layer that provides a barrier to, or limits the absorption of, hydrocarbons. The effects on the polymer of incorporating the nanoclay particles, in particular fracture response, will be detailed.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

The material used in this study comprised a functional polymer, plus the particulate nanoclay filler. A number of organically-modified nanoclays were investigated to determine the optimum combination and loading. Each of the candidate nanocomposites was processed into sheet using a number of established standard polymer processing equipment and a custom-built die, with the objective of identifying preferred routes to compound nanoclay particles into polyolefins.

The absorption properties of the nanocomposites produced were measured indirectly via absorption tests [Figure 1(a)] and a permeability test rig [Figure 1(b)]. The former provides diffusion properties whilst the latter is used to generate an “effective” permeability for the material and requires the use of GCMS.

Figure 1 (a) Absorption test apparatus

Figure 1 (b) Permeability test rig

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results indicate that the use of standard compounding equipment can result in the successful exfoliation of the nanoclays, but low-speed compounding results in better exfoliation of the clays. As discussed below, the exfoliation is sufficient to give the composite material benefits in terms of limiting hydrocarbon absorption.

Absorption measurements demonstrate that a combination of nanoclays blended with functionalised polyethylenes requires a considerably longer time to attain saturation when compared to a single clay nanocomposite of equivalent loading. Informed materials design can reduce the absorption of hydrocarbons in polyolefins. The use of the permeability test provides a very useful method of comparing materials and, ultimately, in selecting the nanocomposite structure with the lowest permeation rate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project appreciatively acknowledges the funding support of the Commission of the European Communities under the Co-operative Action of Framework 6, and support of the participants, namely; Rossi Stamp, Piperec, Icelandic Nanotechnologies, Setec Maschinenbau, ARTS, Contratas Iglesias, Auserpolimeri, Rollepaal, Innovation Center Iceland and Newcastle University.

References:

1. E. Manias, “Nanocomposites: Stiffer by Design”, *Nature Materials*, **6**, 9-11 (2007).